

Genus Distribution for a Graph

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Abstract: In this paper we develop the technique of a distribution decomposition for a graph. A formula is given to determine genus distribution of a cubic graph. Given any connected graph, it is proved that its genus distribution is the sum of those for some cubic graphs by using the technique.

Key Words: Joint tree; genus distribution; embedding distribution; Smarandachely k -drawing.

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§1. Introduction

We consider finite connected graphs. Surfaces are orientable 2-dimensional compact manifolds without boundaries. Embeddings of a graph considered are always assumed to be orientable 2-cell embeddings. Given a graph G and a surface S , a *Smarandachely k -drawing* of G on S is a homeomorphism $\phi: G \rightarrow S$ such that $\phi(G)$ on S has exactly k intersections in $\phi(E(G))$ for an integer k . If $k = 0$, i.e., there are no intersections between in $\phi(E(G))$, or in another words, each connected component of $S - \phi(G)$ is homeomorphic to an open disc, then G has an 2-cell embedding on S . If G can be embedded on surfaces S_r and S_t with genus r and t respectively, then it is shown in [1] that for any k with $r \leq k \leq t$, G has an embedding on S_k . Naturally, the *genus of a graph* is defined to be the minimum genus of a surface on which the graph can be embedded. Given a graph, *how many distinct embeddings does it have on each surface?* This is the genus distribution problem, first investigated by Gross and Furst [4]. As determining the genus of a graph is NP-complete [15], it appears more difficult and significant to determine the genus distribution of a graph.

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There have been results on genus distribution for some particular types of graphs (see [3], [5], [8], [9], [11]-[17], among others). In [6], Liu discovered the joint trees of a graph which provide a substantial foundation for us to solve the genus distribution of a graph. For a given embedding G_σ of a graph G , one can find the surface, embedding surface or associate surface, which G_σ embeds on by applying the associated joint tree. In fact, genus distribution of G is that of the set of all of its embedding surfaces. This paper first study genus distributions of some sets of surfaces and then investigate the genus distribution of a generic graph by using the surface sorting method developed in [16].

Preliminaries will be briefed in the next section. In Section 3, surfaces Q_j^i will be introduced. We shall investigate the genus distribution of surface sets Q_j^0 and Q_j^1 for $1 \leq j \leq 24$, and derive the related recursive formulas. In Section 4, a recursion formula of the genus distribution for a cubic graph is given. In the last section, we show that the genus distribution of a general graph can be transformed into genus distribution of some cubic graphs by using a technique we develop in this paper.

§2. Preliminaries

For a graph G , a *rotation at a vertex v* is a cyclic permutation of edges incident with v . A *rotation system* of G is obtained by giving each vertex of G a rotation. Let ρ_v denote the valence of vertex v which is the number of edges incident with v . The number of rotations systems of G is $\prod_{v \in V(G)} (\rho_v - 1)!$. Edmonds found that there is a bijection between the rotations systems of a graph and its embeddings [2]. Youngs provided the first proof published [18]. Thus, the number of embeddings of G is $\prod_{v \in V(G)} (\rho_v - 1)!$. Let $g_i(G)$ denote the number of embeddings of G with the genus i ($i \geq 0$). Then, the *genus distribution* of G is the sequence $g_0(G), g_1(G), g_2(G), \dots$. The *genus polynomial* of G is $f_G(x) = \sum_{i \geq 0} g_i(G)x^i$.

Given a spanning tree T of G , the joint trees of G are obtained by splitting each non-tree edge e into two semi-edges e and e^- . Given a rotation system σ of G , G_σ , \tilde{T}_σ and \mathcal{P}_T^σ denote the associated embedding, joint tree and embedding surface which G_σ embedded on respectively. There is a bijection between embeddings and joint trees of G such that G_σ corresponds to \tilde{T}_σ . Given a joint tree \tilde{T} , a *sub-joint tree* \tilde{T}_1 of \tilde{T} is a graph consisting of T_1 and semi-edges incident with vertices of T_1 where T_1 is a tree and $V(T_1) \subseteq V(T)$. A sub-joint tree \tilde{T}_1 of \tilde{T} is called *maximal* if there is not a tree T_2 such that $V(T_1) \subset V(T_2) \subseteq V(T)$.

A *linear sequence* $S = abc \dots z$ is a sequence of letters satisfying with a relation $a \prec b \prec c \prec \dots \prec z$. Given two linear sequences S_1 and S_2 , the *difference sequence* S_1/S_2 is obtained by deleting letters of S_2 in S_1 . Since a surface is obtained by identifying a letter with its inverse letter on a special polygon along the direction, a surface is regarded as that polygon such that a and a^- occur only once for each $a \in S$ in this sense.

Let \mathcal{S} be the collection of surfaces. Let $\gamma(S)$ be the genus of a surface S . In order to determine $\gamma(S)$, an equivalence is defined by Op1, Op2 and Op3 on \mathcal{S} as follows:

Op 1. $AB \sim (Ae)(e^-B)$ where $e \notin AB$;

Op 2. $Ae_1e_2Be_2^-e_1^- \sim AeBe^- = Ae^-Be$ where $e \notin AB$;

Op 3. $Aee^-B \sim AB$ where $AB \neq \emptyset$

where AB is a surface.

Thus, S is equivalent to one, and only one of the canonical forms of surfaces $a_0a_0^-$ and $\prod_{k=1}^i a_k b_k a_k^- b_k^-$ which are the sphere and orientable surfaces of genus i ($i \geq 1$).

Lemma 2.1 ([6]) *Let A and B be surfaces. If $a, b \notin B$, and if $A \sim Baba^-b^-$, then $\gamma(A) = \gamma(B) + 1$.*

Lemma 2.2 ([7]) *Let A, B, C, D and E be linear sequences and let $ABCDE$ be a surface. If $a, b \notin ABCDE$, then $AaBbCa^-Db^-E \sim ADCBEaba^-b^-$.*

Lemma 2.3 ([13],[16]) *Let A, B, C and D be linear sequences and let $ABCD$ be a surface. If $a \neq b \neq c \neq a^- \neq b^- \neq c^-$ and if $a, b, c \notin ABCD$, then each of the following holds.*

$$(i) aABa^-CD \sim aBAa^-CD \sim aABa^-DC.$$

$$(ii) AaBa^-bCb^-cDc^- \sim aBa^-AbCb^-cDc^- \sim aBa^-bCb^-AcDc^-.$$

$$(iii) AaBa^-bCb^-cDc^- \sim BaAa^-bCb^-cDc^- \sim CaAa^-bBb^-cDc^- \sim DaAa^-bBb^-cCc^-.$$

For a set of surfaces M , let $g_i(M)$ denote the number of surfaces with the genus i in M . Then, the *genus distribution* of M is the sequence $g_0(M), g_1(M), g_2(M), \dots$. The *genus polynomial* is $f_M(x) = \sum_{i \geq 0} g_i(M)x^i$.

§3. Genus Distribution for Q_j^1

Let $a, b, c, d, a^-, b^-, c^-, d^-$ be distinct letters and let A_0, B_0, C, D_0 be linear sequences. Then, surface sets Q_j^k are defined as follows for $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 24$:

$$\begin{array}{lll} Q_1^k = \{A_k B_k C D_k\} & Q_2^k = \{A_k C D_k a B_k a^-\} & Q_3^k = \{A_k B_k C a D_k a^-\} \\ Q_4^k = \{A_k B_k a C D_k a^-\} & Q_5^k = \{A_k D_k a B_k C a^-\} & Q_6^k = \{A_k D_k C B_k\} \\ Q_7^k = \{B_k C D_k a A_k a^-\} & Q_8^k = \{B_k D_k C a A_k a^-\} & Q_9^k = \{A_k B_k D_k C\} \\ Q_{10}^k = \{A_k D_k C a B_k a^-\} & Q_{11}^k = \{A_k B_k D_k a C a^-\} & Q_{12}^k = \{A_k D_k B_k a C a^-\} \\ Q_{13}^k = \{A_k C B_k D_k\} & Q_{14}^k = \{A_k C B_k a D_k a^-\} & Q_{15}^k = \{A_k C D_k B_k\} \\ Q_{16}^k = \{A_k C a B_k D_k a^-\} & Q_{17}^k = \{A_k D_k B_k C\} & Q_{18}^k = \{C D_k a A_k a^- b B_k b^-\} \\ Q_{19}^k = \{B_k D_k a A_k a^- b C b^-\} & Q_{20}^k = \{B_k C a A_k a^- b D_k b^-\} & Q_{21}^k = \{A_k D_k a B_k a^- b C b^-\} \\ Q_{22}^k = \{A_k C a B_k a^- b D_k b^-\} & Q_{23}^k = \{A_k B_k a C a^- b D_k b^-\} & Q_{24}^k = \{A_k a B_k a^- b C b^- c D_k c^-\} \end{array}$$

where $k = 0$ and 1 , $A_1 \in \{dA_0, A_0d\}$, $(B_1, D_1) \in \{(B_0d^-, D_0), (B_0, d^-D_0)\}$ and $a, a^-, b, b^-, c, c^-, d, d^- \notin ABCD$. Let $f_{Q_j^0}(x)$ denote the genus polynomial of Q_j^0 . If $A_1^0 A_0^0 D_0 B_1 B_2^0 C_2^0 C_1 D_1 = \emptyset$, then $f_{Q_j^0}(x) = 1$. Otherwise, suppose that $f_{Q_j^0}(x)$ are given for $1 \leq j \leq 24$. Then,

Theorem 3.1 *Let $g_{i_j}(n)$ be the number of surfaces with genus i in Q_j^n . Each of the following holds.*

$$g_{i_j}(1) = \begin{cases} g_{i_2}(0) + g_{i_3}(0) + g_{i_4}(0) + g_{i_5}(0), & \text{if } j = 1 \\ g_{i_{21}}(0) + g_{i_{22}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_1}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{15}}(0), & \text{if } j = 2 \\ g_{i_{22}}(0) + g_{i_{23}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_1}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{17}}(0), & \text{if } j = 3 \\ g_{i_4}(0) + g_{i_{18}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_6}(0) + g_{(i-1)_9}(0), & \text{if } j = 4 \\ g_{i_5}(0) + g_{i_{20}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_6}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{13}}(0), & \text{if } j = 5 \\ 2g_{i_6}(0) + 2g_{i_8}(0), & \text{if } j = 6 \\ 2g_{(i-1)_{15}}(0) + 2g_{(i-1)_{17}}(0), & \text{if } j = 7 \text{ and } 16 \\ 4g_{(i-1)_6}(0), & \text{if } j = 8 \\ 2g_{i_4}(0) + 2g_{i_{10}}(0), & \text{if } j = 9 \\ g_{i_{10}}(0) + g_{i_{18}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_6}(0) + g_{(i-1)_9}(0), & \text{if } j = 10 \\ 2g_{i_{21}}(0) + 2g_{i_{23}}(0), & \text{if } j = 11 \\ 2g_{i_{12}}(0) + 2g_{i_{19}}(0), & \text{if } j = 12 \\ 2g_{i_5}(0) + 2g_{i_{14}}(0), & \text{if } j = 13 \\ g_{i_{14}}(0) + g_{i_{20}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_6}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{13}}(0), & \text{if } j = 14 \\ g_{i_7}(0) + g_{i_{12}}(0) + g_{i_{15}}(0) + g_{i_{16}}(0), & \text{if } j = 15 \\ g_{i_7}(0) + g_{i_{12}}(0) + g_{i_{16}}(0) + g_{i_{17}}(0), & \text{if } j = 17 \\ 2g_{(i-1)_4}(0) + 2g_{(i-1)_{10}}(0), & \text{if } j = 18 \\ 4g_{(i-1)_{12}}(0), & \text{if } j = 19 \\ 2g_{(i-1)_5}(0) + 2g_{(i-1)_{14}}(0), & \text{if } j = 20 \\ g_{i_{21}}(0) + g_{i_{24}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{11}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{12}}(0), & \text{if } j = 21 \\ g_{(i-1)_2}(0) + g_{(i-1)_3}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{10}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{14}}(0), & \text{if } j = 22 \\ g_{i_{23}}(0) + g_{i_{24}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{11}}(0) + g_{(i-1)_{12}}(0), & \text{if } j = 23 \\ 2g_{(i-1)_{21}}(0) + 2g_{(i-1)_{23}}(0), & \text{if } j = 24 \end{cases}$$

Proof We shall prove the equation for $g_{i_6}(1)$, and the proofs for others are similar. Let

$$\begin{aligned} U_1 &= \{A_0 d d^- D_0 C B_0\} & U_2 &= \{d A_0 D_0 C B_0 d^-\} \\ U_3 &= \{A_0 d D_0 C B_0 d^-\} & U_4 &= \{d A_0 d^- D_0 C B_0\}. \end{aligned}$$

By the definition of Q_6^1 , we have $Q_6^1 = \{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_4\}$. By the definition of g_i ,

$$g_{i_6}(1) = g_i(U_1) + g_i(U_2) + g_i(U_3) + g_i(U_4).$$

By Op3,

$$A_0 d d^- D_0 C B_0 \sim A_0 D_0 C B_0, \text{ and } d A_0 D_0 C B_0 d^- = A_0 D_0 C B_0 d^- d \sim A_0 D_0 C B_0.$$

It follows that

$$g_i(U_1) = g_i(U_2) = g_{i_6}(0). \quad (8)$$

By Lemma 2.3 (i) and Op2, we have

$$A_0 d D_0 C B_0 d^- = D_0 C B_0 d^- A_0 d \sim B_0 D_0 C d^- A_0 d \sim B_0 D_0 C a A_0 a^-$$

and

$$dA_0d^-D_0CB_0 = B_0D_0CdA_0d^- \sim B_0D_0CaA_0a^-.$$

So

$$g_i(U_3) = g_i(U_4) = g_{i_8}(0). \quad (9)$$

Combining (1) and (2), we have

$$g_{i_6}(1) = 2g_{i_6}(0) + 2g_{i_8}(0).$$

§4. Embedding Surfaces of a Cubic Graph

Given a cubic graph G with n non-tree edges y_l ($1 \leq l \leq n$), suppose that T is a spanning tree such that T contains the longest path of G and that \tilde{T} is an associated joint tree. Let X_l, Y_l, Z_l and F_l be linear sequences for $1 \leq l \leq n$ such that $X_l \cup Y_l = y_l$, $Z_l \cup F_l = y_l^-$, $X_l \neq Y_l$ and $Z_l \neq F_l$.

RECORD RULE: Choose a vertex u incident with two semi-edges as a starting vertex and travel \tilde{T} along with tree edges of \tilde{T} . In order to write down surfaces, we shall consider three cases below.

Case 1: If v is incident with two semi-edges y_s and y_t . Suppose that the linear sequence is R when one arrives v . Then, write down $RX_s y_t Y_s$ going away from v .

Case 2: If v is incident with one semi-edge y_s . Suppose that R_1 is the linear sequence when one arrives v in the first time. Then the sequence is $R_1 X_s$ when one leaves v in the first time. Suppose that R_2 is the linear sequence when one arrives v in the second time. Then the sequence is $R_2 Y_s$ when one leaves v in the second time.

Case 3: If v is not incident with any semi-edge. Suppose that R_1, R_2 and R_3 are, respectively, the linear sequences when one leaves v in the first time, the second time and the third time. Then, the sequences are $(R_2/R_1)R_1(R_3/R_2)$ and R_3 when one leaves v in the third time.

Here, $1 \leq s, t \leq n$ and $s \neq t$. If v is incident with a semi-edge y_s^- , then replace X_s with Z_s and replace Y_s with F_s .

Lemma 4.1 *There is a bijection between embedding surfaces of a cubic graph and surfaces obtained by the record rule.*

Proof Let T be a spanning tree such that \tilde{T} is a joint tree of G above. Suppose that σ_v is

a rotation of v and that R_1, R_2 and R_3 are given above.

$$\sigma_v = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (y_s, y_t, e_r), \text{ if } X_s = y_s \text{ or } F_s = y_s^- \\ \quad \text{and } v \text{ is incident with } y_s, y_t \text{ and } e_r; \\ (y_t, y_s, e_r), \text{ if } Y_s = y_s \text{ or } Z_s = y_s^- \\ \quad \text{and } v \text{ is incident with } y_s, y_t \text{ and } e_r; \\ (y_s, e_1, e_2), \text{ if } X_s = y_s \text{ or } F_s = y_s^- \\ \quad \text{and } v \text{ is incident with } y_s, e_p \text{ and } e_q; \\ (e_1, y_s, e_2), \text{ if } Y_s = y_s \text{ or } Z_s = y_s^- \\ \quad \text{and } v \text{ is incident with } y_s, e_p \text{ and } e_q; \\ (e_1, e_2, e_3), \text{ if the linear sequence is } R_3 \\ \quad \text{and } v \text{ is incident with } e_p, e_q \text{ and } e_r; \\ (e_2, e_1, e_3), \text{ if the linear sequence is } (R_2/R_1)R_1(R_3/R_2) \\ \quad \text{and } v \text{ is incident with } e_p, e_q \text{ and } e_r \end{array} \right.$$

where e_p, e_q and e_r are tree-edges for $1 \leq p, q, r \leq 2n-3$ and $e_p \neq e_q \neq e_r$ for $p \neq q \neq r$. Hence the conclusion holds. \square

By the definitions for X_l, Y_l, Z_l and F_l , we have the following observation:

Observation 4.2 A surface set $H^{(0)}$ of G has properties below.

- (1) Either $X_l, Y_l \in H^{(0)}$ or $X_l, Y_l \notin H^{(0)}$;
- (2) Either $Z_l, F_l \in H^{(0)}$ or $Z_l, F_l \notin H^{(0)}$;
- (3) If for some l with $1 \leq l \leq n$, $X_l, Y_l, Z_l, F_l \in H^{(0)}$, then $H^{(0)}$ has one of the following forms $X_l A^{(0)} Y_l B^{(0)} Z_l C^{(0)} F_l D^{(0)}$, $Y_l A^{(0)} X_l B^{(0)} Z_l C^{(0)} F_l D^{(0)}$, $X_l A^{(0)} Y_l B^{(0)} F_l C^{(0)} Z_l D^{(0)}$ or $Y_l A^{(0)} X_l B^{(0)} F_l C^{(0)} Z_l D^{(0)}$. These forms are regarded to have no difference through this paper.

If either $X_l \in H^{(0)}, Z_l \notin H^{(0)}$ or $X_l \notin H^{(0)}, Z_l \in H^{(0)}$, then replace X_l, Y_l, Z_l and F_l according to the definition of X_l, Y_l, Z_l and F_l .

RECURSION RULE: Given a surface set $H^{(0)} = \{X_l A^{(0)} Y_l B^{(0)} Z_l C^{(0)} F_l D^{(0)}\}$ where $A^{(0)}, B^{(0)}, C^{(0)}$ and $D^{(0)}$ are linear sequences.

Step 1. Let $A_0 = A^{(0)}, B_0 = B^{(0)}, C_0 = C^{(0)}$ and $D_0 = D^{(0)}$. Q_j^1 is obtained for $2 \leq j \leq 5$. Then $H_j^{(1)}$ is obtained by replacing a, a^- and Q_j^1 with a_1, a_1^- and $H_j^{(1)}$ respectively.

Step 2. Given a surface set $H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_k}^{(k)}$ for a positive integer k and $2 \leq j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_k \leq 5$, without loss of generality, suppose that $H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_k}^{(k)} = \{X_s A^{(k)} Y_s B^{(k)} Z_s C^{(k)} F_s D^{(k)}\}$ where $A^{(k)}, B^{(k)}, C^{(k)}$ and $D^{(k)}$ are linear sequences for certain s ($1 \leq s \leq n$). Let $A_0 = A^{(k)}, B_0 = B^{(k)}, C_0 = C^{(k)}$ and $D_0 = D^{(k)}$. Q_j^1 is obtained for $2 \leq j \leq 5$. Then $H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_k, j}^{(k+1)}$ is obtained by replacing a, a^- and Q_j^1 with a_{k+1}, a_{k+1}^- and $H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_k, j}^{(k+1)}$ respectively.

Some surface sets $H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_m}^{(m)}$ which contain a_l, a_l^-, y_l, y_l^- can be obtained by using step 2 for a positive integer m , $2 \leq j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_m \leq 5$ and $1 \leq l \leq n$. It is easy to compute $f_{H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_m}^{(m)}}(x)$.

By Theorem 3.7,

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_i(H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_r}^{(r)}) &= g_i(H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_r, 2}^{(r+1)}) + g_i(H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_r, 3}^{(r+1)}) \\
 &+ g_i(H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_r, 4}^{(r+1)}) + g_i(H_{j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_r, 5}^{(r+1)}), \quad (1) \\
 &\text{if } 0 \leq r \leq m-1, 2 \leq j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_r \leq 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig.1: G_0 and \tilde{T}_0

Example 4.3 The graph G_0 is given in Fig.1. A joint tree \tilde{T}_0 is obtained by splitting non-tree edges y_l ($1 \leq l \leq 6$). Travel \tilde{T}_0 by regarded v_0 as a starting point. By using record rule we obtain surface sets

$$\{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 Z_2 Z_3 y_3 F_3 Y_6 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 X_6 F_2 F_1\}$$

and

$$\{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 Z_2 Y_6 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 X_6 F_2 F_1 Z_3 y_3 F_3\}.$$

By replacing Z_2, F_2, Z_3, F_3, X_6 and Y_6 according the definition 16 surface sets U_r ($1 \leq r \leq 16$) are listed below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_1 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_2^- y_3^- y_3 y_6 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 F_1\} \\
 U_2 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_2^- y_3^- y_3 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 y_6 F_1\} \\
 U_3 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_2^- y_3 y_3^- y_6 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 F_1\} \\
 U_4 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_2^- y_3 y_3^- Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 y_6 F_1\} \\
 U_5 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_3^- y_3 y_6 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 y_2^- F_1\} \\
 U_6 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_3^- y_3 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 y_6 y_2^- F_1\} \\
 U_7 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_3 y_3^- y_6 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 y_2^- F_1\} \\
 U_8 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_3 y_3^- Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 y_6 y_2^- F_1\} \\
 U_9 &= \{X_1 y_2 Y_1 Z_1 y_2^- y_6 Y_5 Y_4 Z_5 Z_4 y_6^- F_4 F_5 X_4 X_5 F_1 y_3^- y_3\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{10} &= \{X_1y_2Y_1Z_1y_2^-Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5y_6F_1y_3^-y_3\} \\
U_{11} &= \{X_1y_2Y_1Z_1y_2^-y_6Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5F_1y_3y_3^-\} \\
U_{12} &= \{X_1y_2Y_1Z_1y_2^-Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5y_6F_1y_3y_3^-\} \\
U_{13} &= \{X_1y_2Y_1Z_1y_6Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5y_2^-F_1y_3^-y_3\} \\
U_{14} &= \{X_1y_2Y_1Z_1Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5y_6y_2^-F_1y_3^-y_3\} \\
U_{15} &= \{X_1y_2Y_1Z_1y_6Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5y_2^-F_1y_3y_3^-\} \\
U_{16} &= \{X_1y_2Y_1Z_1Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5y_6y_2^-F_1y_3y_3^-\}.
\end{aligned}$$

The genus distribution of U_r can be obtained by using the recursion rule. Since the method is similar, we shall calculate the genus distribution of U_1 and leave the calculation of genus distribution for others to readers.

U_1 is reduced to $\{X_1y_2Y_1Z_1y_2^-y_6Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5F_1\}$ by Op2. Let $H^{(0)} = S_1$, $A_0 = y_2$, $C_0 = y_2^-y_6Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5$ and $B_0 = D_0 = \emptyset$. Then $H_2^{(1)} = H_3^{(1)} = \{y_2y_2^-y_6Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5\}$ and $H_4^{(1)} = H_5^{(1)} = \{y_2a_1y_2^-y_6Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5a_1^-\}$.

$H_2^{(1)}$ is reduced to $\{y_6Y_5Y_4Z_5Z_4y_6^-F_4F_5X_4X_5\}$ by Op2. Let $A_0 = X_5y_6Y_5$, $B_0 = Z_5$, $C_0 = y_6^-$ and $D_0 = F_5$. Then $H_{2,2}^{(2)} = \{X_5y_6Y_5y_6^-F_5a_2Z_5a_2^-\}$, $H_{2,3}^{(2)} = \{X_5y_6Y_5Z_5y_6^-a_2F_5a_2^-\}$, $H_{2,4}^{(2)} = \{X_5y_6Y_5Z_5a_2y_6^-F_5a_2^-\}$ and $H_{2,5}^{(2)} = \{X_5y_6Y_5F_5a_2Z_5y_6^-a_2^-\}$. $H_{4,2}^{(2)} = \{X_5a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6Y_5y_6^-F_5a_2Z_5a_2^-\}$, $H_{4,3}^{(2)} = \{X_5a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6Y_5Z_5y_6^-a_2F_5a_2^-\}$, $H_{4,4}^{(2)} = \{X_5a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6Y_5Z_5a_2y_6^-F_5a_2^-\}$ and $H_{4,5}^{(2)} = \{X_5a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6Y_5F_5a_2Z_5y_6^-a_2^-\}$ by letting $A_0 = X_5a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6Y_5$, $B_0 = Z_5$, $C_0 = y_6^-$ and $D_0 = F_5$.

Similarly, $H_{2,2,2}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_2a_2^-a_3y_6^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{2,2,3}^{(3)} = \{y_6y_6^-a_2a_3a_2^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{2,2,4}^{(3)} = \{y_6y_6^-a_3a_2a_2^-a_3^-\}$ and $H_{2,2,5}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_2^-a_3y_6^-a_2a_3^-\}$. $H_{2,3,2}^{(3)} = \{y_6y_6^-a_2a_2^-\}$, $H_{2,3,3}^{(3)} = \{y_6y_6^-a_2a_3a_2^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{2,3,4}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_3y_6^-a_2a_2^-a_3^-\}$ and $H_{2,3,5}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_2^-a_3y_6^-a_2a_3^-\}$. $H_{2,4,2}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_2y_6^-a_2^-\}$, $H_{2,4,3}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_2y_6^-a_3a_2^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{2,4,4}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_3a_2y_6^-a_2^-a_3^-\}$ and $H_{2,4,5}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_2^-a_3a_2y_6^-a_3^-\}$. $H_{2,5,2}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_2y_6^-a_2^-\}$, $H_{2,5,3}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_2a_3y_6^-a_2^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{2,5,4}^{(3)} = \{y_6a_3a_2y_6^-a_2^-a_3^-\}$ and $H_{2,5,5}^{(3)} = \{y_6y_6^-a_2^-a_3a_2a_3^-\}$. $H_{4,2,2}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_2a_2^-a_3y_6^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{4,2,3}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6y_6^-a_2a_3a_2^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{4,2,4}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6y_6^-a_3a_2a_2^-a_3^-\}$ and $H_{4,2,5}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_2^-a_3y_6^-a_2a_3^-\}$. $H_{4,3,2}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6y_6^-a_2a_2^-\}$, $H_{4,3,3}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6y_6^-a_2a_3a_2^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{4,3,4}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_3y_6^-a_2a_2^-a_3^-\}$ and $H_{4,3,5}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_2^-a_3y_6^-a_2a_3^-\}$. $H_{4,4,2}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_2y_6^-a_2^-\}$, $H_{4,4,3}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_2y_6^-a_3a_2^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{4,4,4}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_3a_2^-a_3^-\}$ and $H_{4,4,5}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_2^-a_3y_6^-a_2a_3^-\}$. $H_{4,5,2}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_2y_6^-a_2^-\}$, $H_{4,5,3}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_2a_3y_6^-a_2^-a_3^-\}$, $H_{4,5,4}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6a_3a_2y_6^-a_2^-a_3^-\}$ and $H_{4,5,5}^{(3)} = \{a_1^-y_2a_1y_2^-y_6y_6^-a_2^-a_3a_2a_3^-\}$.

By using (1),

$$f_{U_1}(x) = 4 + 32x + 28x^2.$$

Thus,

$$f_{G_0}(x) = 64 + 512x + 448x^2.$$

§5. Genus Distribution for a Graph

Theorem 5.1 *Given a graph, the genus distribution of G is determined by using the genus distribution of some cubic graphs.*

Proof Given a finite graph G_0 , suppose that u is adjacent to $k+1$ distinct vertices $v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k$ of G_0 with $k \geq 3$. Actually, the supposition always holds by subdividing some edges of G .

A *distribution decomposition* of a graph is defined below: add a vertex u_s of valence 3 such that u_s is adjacent to u, v_0 and v_s for each s with $1 \leq s \leq k$ and then obtain a graph G_s by deleting the edges uv_0 and uv_s .

Choose the spanning trees T_s of G_s such that uv_s, uu_s and $u_s v_s$ are tree edges for $0 \leq s \leq k$. Consider a joint tree \tilde{T}_0 of G . Let \tilde{T}_s^* be the maximal joint tree of \tilde{T}_0 such that $v_s \in V(T_s^*)$ and $v_t \notin V(T_s^*)$ for $t \neq s$ and $0 \leq s, t \leq k$.

Let v_s be the starting vertex of \tilde{T}_s^* for $0 \leq s \leq k$. Suppose that \mathcal{A}_s is the set of all sequences by travelling \tilde{T}_s^* and that Q_s is the embedding surface set of G_s . Then

$$Q_0 = \{A_0 A_{r_1} A_{r_2} A_{r_3} \cdots A_{r_k} \mid A_{r_p} \in \mathcal{A}_{r_p}, 1 \leq r_p \leq k, r_p \neq r_q \text{ for } p \neq q\}$$

and for $1 \leq s \leq k$

$$Q_s = \{A_0 A_s A_{r_1} A_{r_2} A_{r_3} \cdots A_{r_{k-1}}, A_0 A_{r_1} A_{r_2} A_{r_3} \cdots A_{r_{k-1}} A_s \mid A_{r_p} \in \mathcal{A}_{r_p}, \\ 1 \leq r_p \leq k, r_p \neq s, 1 \leq p, q \leq k-1, \text{ and } r_p \neq r_q \text{ for } p \neq q\}.$$

Let $f_{Q_s}(x)$ denote the genus distribution of Q_s . It is obvious that

$$f_{Q_0}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=1}^k f_{Q_s}(x).$$

Thus,

$$f_{G_0}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=1}^k f_{G_s}(x).$$

Since G_0 has finite vertices, the genus distribution of G_0 can be transformed into those of some cubic graphs in homeomorphism by using the distribution decomposition. \square

Next we give a simple application of Theorem 5.1.

Example 5.2 The graph W_4 is shown in Fig.2. In order to calculate its genus distribution, we use the distribution decomposition and then we obtain three graph G_s for $1 \leq s \leq 3$ (Fig.2). It is obvious that G_2 are isomorphic to Möbius ladder ML_3 and G_s are isomorphic to Ringel ladder RL_2 for $s = 1$ and 3. Since (see [8], [15])

$$f_{ML_3}(x) = 40x + 24x^2$$

and since (see [9], [15])

$$f_{RL_2}(x) = 2 + 38x + 24x^2,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{W_4}(x) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=1}^3 f_{G_s}(x) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} [40x + 24x^2 + 2(2 + 38x + 24x^2)] \\
 &= 2 + 58x + 36x^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig.2: W_4 and G_s

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